

Music, Dementia, and Music Education: Bringing Music Where It's Needed

Cameron Armstrong

Music Education, University of Washington

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Abstract

Research suggests music listening and engagement have profound effects on people battling dementia. Music educators are members of society that possess privileged resources regarding musical knowledge, ability, and access, and are distinctly situated to provide transformational experiences to those with dementia. However, the daily responsibilities and considerations of music educators fall largely outside of these populations. This paper seeks to first, impose cosmopolitanism as a framework for music education as theorized by Niknafs (2020) in effort to elucidate ethical reasons for music educators and their students to look beyond the K-12 classroom and consider musically engaging those with dementia; and second, to investigate ways for music educators (and their students) to provide life giving musical experiences to those with dementia while in turn, creating new and reciprocal learning experiences for everyone involved. In addition, alternative practical applications of cosmopolitanism music education are discussed.

Keywords: dementia, cosmopolitan music education, intergenerational music making

Preprint

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It was a brisk October day, and I, a young musician and music educator had found myself at a dementia care facility where I had been hired to play music for an hour. As I set up my instruments, I was greeted by 30 wheelchairs, each occupied by residents with vacant eyes and sunken postures. Many could no longer communicate with verbal language and sat in silence. It was a stark contrast to the outside world. Halfway through the set I vividly recall playing the notable jazz tune St. James Infirmary Blues, a song made popular by Louis Armstrong and his Orchestra in 1928. As I sang, I noticed the eyes of residents light up. A man who had appeared to be lifeless and immobile began moving back and forth in his wheelchair, only before unexpectedly opening his mouth to hum along. As I concluded the last verse, the room began to applaud. Suddenly, a woman in the front row by the name of Ella began to speak. "I love that song" she said, "I would listen to it on the radio as a child growing up. I'll have to tell my mother that I heard you play it today." As she spoke, her husband (who did not suffer from dementia) bluntly informed Ella that her mother had died 20 years ago. She looked at him stunned and frustrated, but then turned her attention back to me and said, "I love how you sing the song, however it's 'so good, so cold, so fair.'—I had sung the words wrong; she was correcting me.

As I left the care facility that day, I was blindsided by the impact that music had on those suffering from dementia. It was a profound reminder of the power that music has on humanity, and the responsibilities of those who wield it. I realized in that moment that many musicians and educators may be missing crucial opportunities to significantly impact the lives of those with dementia, and in the process provide their students with valuable learning experiences.

Ella was suffering from late stages of dementia. The disease had ravaged her brain. With brain cells permanently damaged, her ability to recall even the most important of memories, like the passing of her mother, were lost. The loss of episodic memory can be devastating for a person's sense of personal identity as well as their ability to learn new skills (Klein & Nichols, 2012; Quinn & Blandon, 2017). However, Ella's ability to remember the words to St. James Infirmary Blues over her mother's death was not a coincidence. A great wealth of research suggests that music has the capability to recover lost

musical melodies as well as the emotions and autobiographical memories associated with them (Cuddy et al., 2012; Fornazzari et al., 2006; Hsieh, Hornberger, Piguet, & Hodges, 2011; Omar, Hailstone, & Warren, 2012; Rasmussen et al., 2009). Moreover, people with dementia have been able to temporarily regain parts of their identity, learn, and improve their overall quality of life through the process of exposure and participation to music (Cuddy, Sikka, Silveira, Bai and Vanstone, Walla, 2017; Haj et al., 2011; Quinn & Blandon, 2017). Amazingly, music educators have the ability to harness the power of music to improve the lives of people like Ella in ways that healthcare workers may not. However, the daily responsibilities and considerations of most music educators often fall outside of these populations. The purpose of this paper is to understand music education not just as a profession, but as a lifestyle that orbits both the local and the global, and most importantly is driven by an ethical orientation centering human connection. This perspective positions music educators as mobile musicians that willingly transcend the walls of the traditional classroom to reach those who lie beyond, ultimately using their assets to bring music wherever it is needed. Further, this paper explores ways that music educators and their students can embody this “lifestyle” by musically engaging those with dementia in various contexts.

Dementia

Dementia is not a specific disease but is rather a “general term for the impaired ability to remember, think, or make decisions that interferes with doing everyday activities” (CDC, 2021). Dementia includes Alzheimers, Frontotemporal disorders, and Lewy Body. Each is an incurable neurodegenerative disorder that results in progressive and irreversible loss of neurons and brain function (NIH, 2021). Alzheimers is the most common form of dementia resulting in the loss of a sense of self, communication and general well being. The disease affects 46.8 million, primarily older adults, world wide (CDC, 2021), and the disease is only becoming more prevalent. By 2030, 1-5 Americans are projected to be 65 years and older (RHHub, 2021). Moreover, instances of Alzheimers are expected to grow from 6.1 million (2020) to 8.5 million by 2030 (Gaugler et al., 2021), and consequently, the need for those willing to assist in effective interventions that raise the quality of life of populations battling

dementia is only becoming more urgent. Musicians and music educators may have the resources and skill sets to help in this effort in ways that other members of society can not.

Improving Lives through Music Listening and Engagement

Research regarding music and its capacity to improve the lives of those with dementia is robust; music can help recall forgotten musical melodies (Cuddy et al., 2012; Fornazzari et al., 2006; Hsieh, Hornberger, Piguet, & Hodges, 2011; Omar, Hailstone, & Warren, 2012), lost positive autobiographical memories (Rasmussen & Berntsen, 2009), and in the process help those with dementia to regain a sense of self-identity that had faded in the absence of their foundational recollections (Cuddy, Sikka, Silveira, Bai and Vanstone, Walla, 2017; El Haj et al., 2011). Moreover, bringing music and music participation to residents at dementia care facilities, live music in particular (Holmes et al., 2006; Götell, 2009), but also, recordings (Götell, 2009; Good, Anderson, Stanton-Hicks, Grass, & Makii, 2002) can enhance mood (Götell, 2009), communication ability (Ledger and Baker, 2007), self-consciousness (Arroyo-Anlló, 2013), and even reduce physical pain (Good, Anderson, Stanton-Hicks, Grass, & Makii, 2002) and levels of aggression towards others (Hicks-Moore, 2005). Further, sometimes live music is the *only* intervention that can pull someone with dementia out of an aggressive and delusional state (Garadebian, 2019).

Engaging collaboratively with those suffering from dementia may also have the positive implications of all involved. Research suggests intergenerational musical encounters and collaborations between those with dementia and young musicians can be successful in partnership with college students, K-12 students, and even infants. Moreover, recommended research-based intergenerational musical activities include choir (Harris & Capporell, 2014), songwriting (Dusman, 2020), singing nursery rhythms (McLennan, 2019), and 'person-centered' musical improvisations (Smilde et al., 2014). Activity outcomes are very much aligned with values of cosmopolitanism, with major findings rooted in intergenerational human connection between respective groups, and students in particular showing increased empathy, self-reflection (Smilde et al., 2014), a decrease in stigmatization towards those with dementia (Conway & Hodgman, 2008), and an honoring of diverse routes to creativity (Dusman, 2020).

In addition, intergenerational musical engagement can lead to heightened confidence, social skills, and musical skills in all participants (McLennan, 2019).

Distinguishing Music Educators from Music Therapists

Musicians and music educators often see those with dementia as outside of their purview, and leave musical engagement with the elderly to music therapists. Despite the division between fields, both have a role to play in helping those with dementia. United in the use of music to better people's lives, music education and music therapy are sometimes conflated, however they are distinct professions. Music therapists are embedded in the medical field, and rooted in clinical, evidence-based interventions to achieve non-musical therapeutic goals through music, where music education is centered around evidence-based music teaching and learning to achieve musical goals.

Music therapy regards the “clinical & evidence-based use of music interventions to accomplish individualized goals within a therapeutic relationship by a credentialed professional who has completed an approved music therapy program” (American Music Therapy Association, 2021). The profession is clinical and research-based, meaning that it is grounded in the medical field and utilized as a medical practice. Music therapy focuses on individuals and their health, using research-based approaches to achieving non-musical therapeutic goals. These goals can include but are not limited to, decreasing pain, improving coping skills, increasing social interaction and self-expression, offering emotional and spiritual support, facilitating and improving expression, increasing relaxation and providing distraction, decreasing restlessness and agitation, enhancing memory and reminiscence, and assisting in physical rehabilitation. Further, individuals are cared for within a therapeutic relationship, meaning therapists are intentionally building a connection with clients/patients/students. Music therapy takes place in a range of medical and educational settings with all ages. Lastly, music therapists are board-certified, and must complete 100 hours of continuing education every year, on top of completing an accredited music therapy training program.

Music education is a profession primarily concerned with the teaching and learning of music. The field measures success in musical proficiency, and focuses on the skill sets included but not limited to

music fundamentals, music performance, music theory, and music history. Moreover, music education is focused on group learning and in many cases operates within an ensemble setting. The formal field of music education has historically focused on k-12 learners in schools (Lehmberg and Fung, 2010), with adults outside of school receiving little attention (Myers, 1995), and those with dementia often forgotten. Goals regarding healing and well being have rarely been a priority for the field however calls have been made for a more ‘therapeutic music education’ “where educators also recognize therapeutic potential, and students achieve personal growth alongside musical growth” (Mitchell, 2016, p.19)—centering the humanity of the student.

Despite extant research illuminating the powerful relationship between music and those with dementia, these elderly populations have been excluded from music education. By playing music for, and engaging young students with those battling dementia, musicians and music educators have the potential to raise the quality of life of those facing the hardships of aging and neurodegeneration. However, a new framework will need to be adopted in order to understand the title “music educator” as not just a job, but as a lifestyle driven by human connection, and the responsibility to bring music where it’s needed. This paper seeks to first, impose cosmopolitanism as a framework for music education as theorized by Niknafs (2020) in effort to elucidate ethical reasons for music educators and their students to look beyond the K-12 classroom and consider musically engaging those with dementia; and second, to investigate ways for music educators (and their students) to provide life giving musical experiences to those with dementia while in turn, creating new and reciprocal learning experiences for everyone involved.

Cosmopolitan Music Education Framework

Cosmopolitanism, as defined by Niknafs (2020), in essence involves centering human connection and seeing commonalities. As a framework for music education, cosmopolitanism can be used to understand the importance of including those with dementia into the hearts, minds, practices and purview of music educators. Cosmopolitan music education sees the field through a more “holistic lens” and calls for teachers to transcend the sonic context of genres and pedagogies in specific teaching situations to prioritize human connections and illuminate “what humans share despite their differences” (Nikanfs,

2020, p.14). The framework is founded on the premise that music education has the power to rectify harm that humans impinge upon themselves and others, and that “music education is part of the very personal and individual essence of what it means to be human” (Heimonen, 2012 p.75).

Cosmopolitanism and its multifarious meanings generally refer to an engagement with the world guided by a sense of global citizenship. In common vernacular the word has referred to the elite or privileged and their outlook on the world. Further, “cosmopolitan” has been synonymous with the educated, while those who display ignorance are considered provincial (Bates, 2014). However, one of the four definitions offered by Merriam-Webster’s dictionary provides a different perspective— “found in most parts of the world and under varied ecological conditions” (Niknafs, 2020). In the context of education, this definition can remind us that learners are everywhere and learning takes place in varied ecological conditions, many of which fall outside of formal school grounds. Expanding on Merriam-Webster’s definition, Niknafs (2020) pulls from both Appiah’s (2007) moral cosmopolitanism and Appaduris’ (2013) ‘cosmopolitan from below’ to derive a philosophy that “highlights the significance of the human connection...inherent in, and possibly the most prominent aspect of music education practices” (Niknafs, 2020, p.3).

Gazing at an ever globalizing world, Appiah (2007) imagines cosmopolitanism in two intertwining strands: (1) obligation to others, and (2) “that we take seriously the value of not just human life but of particular human lives” (p.26). The cosmopolitan person simultaneously embraces the at times clashing ideals of universal concern for others and respect for human differences. For Appiah, obligations to others “stretch beyond those to whom we are related by the ties of kith and kind, or even the more formal ties of a shared citizenship” (p.25). Moreover, Appiah’s cosmopolitanism suggests that we value not just human life, but particular lives; i.e., embracing humans and their differences and “taking an interest in the practices and beliefs that lend them significance” (p.27). Further, connecting with those humans outside of our social sphere, or those who do not share our intersecting identities such as nation, lifestyle, or religion requires approaching situations with a curiosity, finding inevitable commonalities that

ultimately can lead to new discoveries, as “we can learn from one another; or we can simply be intrigued by alternative ways of thinking, feeling, and acting”(p.195).

Similarly, Appaduris’ (2013) “cosmopolitanism frombelow” urges the expansion of one’s own personal and cultural horizons in effort to connectwith a broader vision of the world and wider senseof human values. This view of cosmopolitanism “beginsclose to home and builds on the practices of the local, the everyday, and the familiar, but is imbuedwith a politics of hope that requires the stretchingof the boundaries of the everyday in a variety of politicaldirections” (p.198). It aims to “combat indignities and exclusions” (p.198) by producing “a preferredgeography of the global by the strategic extensionof local cultural horizons” (p.198).

Cosmopolitanism argues that music educators shouldbe guided by their moral intuition to connect musically and on a human level with thosewho face distress, regardless of where in the world they reside in effort to combat these “indignitiesand exclusions;” further, they consider those whohave been marginalized from music engagement as a resultof their psychological and “ecological conditions.” Through cosmopolitanism, “music education becomesa lifestyle—whose participants cultivate their ethical sensitivities toward human connection” andin doing so, cultivate “the capacity to alleviatethe human sufferings occurring globally” (Niknafs, 2020,p.3). With the engagement of vulnerable and marginalized populations “music teachers in collaborationwith students can select a shared capacity of human experience...to explore the relational interchangesbetween humans—and non-humans..and examine how individuals of all walks of life and invarious corners of the world make sense of their experiences in and through sound and music” (Niknafs,2020, p.14).

The exploration of these relational interchanges betweenthose with dementia can be seen as a new way of defining the limits and intention of musiceducation. It challenges educators to “stretch beyond those to whom we are related by the ties ofkith and kind (p.25)” as Appiah (2007) suggests,and see those with dementia as humans to connect withemotionally, spiritually, intellectually, and musically; this requires a pedagogical and ethical approach definedby an intrigue for “alternative ways of thinking, feeling and acting” (p.25). Further, connecting withthese distinct populations by reaching out to local

care facilities is in alignment with Appaduris' (2013) call for a “strategic extension of local cultural horizons” (p.198), as an effort to build towards “globalaffinities and solidarities through an irregular assortment of near and distant experiences” (p.198),neither assuming nor denying the value of their universality. In other words, educators may learnmore about human connection and the human condition around the world by engaging with local communitieslike those suffering from dementia, that are different in kind, however embody a shared humanityand hold great insight into what it means to be human—This is the ultimate learning experience formusicians, students, educators and those with dementia alike.

Through engaging these marginalized communities, thosewith neurodegeneration can learn to engage musically, and music educators and their studentscan develop deeper knowledge of music's relationship to the human condition, and to thosewhose reality is so disparate from their own (Smilde et al, 2014). Those suffering from dementia experiencethe world differently; the past, present and futureare always entangled, mere moments can last an eternity,and years can move by in the blink of an eye—and those who live with dementia exist and learn in aconstant “reconstruction of selfhood” and “state of becoming.” (Quinn & Blandon, 2017, p.21); i.e., theylive and learn in the moment. In working with those who have dementia, educators and students can developa deeper understanding of human dignity and equity, while further provoking reflections on personalidentity and motivation (Smilde et al, 2014), as they center their teaching and learning in a “sharedcapacity for human experience” (Niknafs, 2020, p.14). Moreover, by situating music education in a cosmopolitanframework of “human connection,” the possibilities of spaces to engagein and persons to engagewithdramatically expand the learning opportunities for educators, students and participantsalike.Regarding praxis, cosmopolitan music education can manifest in many forms however, formusic educators working in pre-k through university level, bringing students to care facilities to perform,or collaboratively engaging those with dementia musically is a good place to start.

Bringing Music and Musical Participation to Those with Dementia

Cosmopolitan music education provides justification for music educators to use their skills and resources to benefit those with dementia by bringing K-12 students to perform for, or engage collaboratively with those in care facilities. In western European culture, elders are pushed to the periphery of society, forgotten by the youthful and able, and those who suffer from dementia in some cases have even forgotten themselves. Musicians and music educators can contribute to these communities by bringing young students to perform at care facilities. Moreover, research suggests that interactive and intergenerational musical activities have beneficial outcomes for both K-12 students and those with dementia (Dusman, 2020; Harris & Capporella, 2014, 2018; Riley, 2009). Further, positive effects of music therapy practices, and the training of caretakers in musical practices, have been shown to be beneficial to those with dementia (Särkämö et al., 2014); however, the presence of a musical therapist at care facilities as well as regular music training for staff is severely limited across the country with approximately 8,000 board certified music therapists in the United States (American Music Therapy Association 2), and 28,900 residential care communities (CDC, 2021). Music educators have the luxury and ability to affect the quality of life of human beings, and with that power comes a responsibility to help those in need. In the absence of musical resources and outlets for those with dementia, music educators can use their agency and access to music to create musical learning experiences for those with dementia and for the youthful musicians who engage them.

Students Performing at Care Facilities

Bringing students to perform in care facilities can dramatically affect the wellbeing of those with dementia. The presence of student performers can be beneficial, as live music in particular has been shown to induce positive effects in comparison to pre-recorded music. For those with dementia, the simple act of listening to music can bring back memories of the past, elevate the mood of the listener, improve communication skills, and even reduce physical pain. Moreover, sometimes music is the only intervention that can pull someone with dementia out of deep psychological suffering.

Something Special About Live Music

Both live and background music can be used to elicit and enhance positive emotions in those with dementia, however live performances may provide benefits that recordings do not. Amazingly, background music has been shown to diminish aggression in elderly listeners, and increase a sense of playfulness; yet, live singing from a caregiver is shown to “enhance a sense of sincerity and intimacy in the interaction” (Götell, 2009, p.1). In a study by Holmes et al., (2006), live interactive music was compared with pre-recorded music regarding its ability to reduce apathy in those with varying levels of dementia. The majority of subjects (69%) showed positive engagement to live music, regardless of dementia severity, however only 25% of subjects showed positive engagement with pre-recorded music. Findings suggest that bringing live musicians to perform for those at care facilities can significantly affect the wellbeing of residents, and pre-recorded music, while not harmful, is not as clearly beneficial.

Music Listening and Cognitive Phenomena

Students’ performances at care facilities may have miraculous cognitive effects on those with dementia. The act of listening to music from one’s past may recall long lost positive musical and autobiographical memories in those with even late stage dementia (Rasmussen & Berntsen, 2009). Further, these listening experiences can recover lost fragments of self-identity among those suffering from neural degeneration, as memories of significant life events come flooding back, e.g., formative childhood experiences, a college graduation, a wedding day, or landing a dream job (Cuddy, Sikka, Silveira, Bai and Vanstone, Walla, 2017; El Haj et al., 2011). Moreover, Arroyo-Anlló (2013) suggests familiar music acts as an enhancer of self-consciousness in patients with Alzheimer’s. Cognitive benefits received from music interventions may extend to an improved retention of communication ability among those with dementia (Ledger and Baker, 2007). In response to these research findings, music educators should not only bring students to care facilities to perform, but should consider the residents they will be performing for and attempt to gather information about the age range and demographics. Picking repertoire that coincides with the youthful years of the audience may evoke life giving memories that are otherwise inaccessible.

Music and Relieving Psychological Suffering

Sometimes, live music is the *only* intervention that can help someone suffering from dementia. In an autoethnography by Garabedian (2019), she describes a distressed care facility resident (Robert) who was deemed unreachable by care staff. As a last resort, the onsite doctor called Garabedian to come play cello for the man. For over an hour, she performed traditional Scottish music for him as he slowly found his way back from the agitated and readily violent state he was living in—music was the *only* intervention that could bring him back from his dark internal world. She specifically played Scottish music as a way to appeal to what Kitwood (1997) refers to as Robert's basic human needs: "*occupation* (with the music); *inclusion* (with [performer] and others who shared the music with him); *identity* (derived from familiar Scottish music); *comfort* (derived from familiar Scottish music); and *attachment* (the familiar Scottish music likely helped draw him back into his real life)" (Garabedian, 2019, p.2878). Further, Robert's reaction was what Garabedian (2014) would call an embodied sense of 'haven' "... a capturing and holding" of his attention, transporting him "either back in time, or entirely out of time and a state of flow, or into an intense musical experience" (Garabedian, 2014, p.vi; also see Garabedian & Kelly, 2020). Garabedian was not a physician or music therapist, but a college musician.

Music and Relieving Physical Suffering

Performing music for the elderly, including those with dementia can also be physically and psychologically beneficial to care facility residents. Chamber music has been shown to reduce physical pain and increase mood in older adults. In addition, psycho-social benefits including enjoyment, engagement, meaning & connection were found. Similarly, a study by McCaffery & Freedman (2003) suggests that listening to music is an effective intervention for the reduction of chronic osteoarthritis pain for community-dwelling elders. Further, listening to music (i.e., relaxation recordings) can lead to significantly less post-test pain following a surgery (Good, Anderson, Stanton-Hicks, Grass, & Makii, 2002). In addition, music listening has effects on bodily behavior in those with dementia including a reduction of verbal and physical aggression towards others.

As music educators, bringing students to perform in care facilities has the potential to significantly increase residents' quality of life while simultaneously giving students an opportunity to

perform in public. Having performing opportunities is a significant part of developing performance skills in young musicians (Meissner, 2020). Contextualizing these performances through a cosmopolitan view, students should additionally take the opportunity to connect with their audience's disposition, and actively engage in “the politics of hope, the capacity to aspire and with being utterly human” (Niknafs, 2020, p.4). The dichotomy of performing music for those with dementia can have powerfully positive implications, however research suggests directly engaging those facing neural degeneration in intergenerational music making may yield even deeper benefits for all involved.

Engaging Collaboratively with Those Suffering from Dementia at Care Facilities

Engaging musically and collaboratively with those suffering from dementia can be a transformative experience for all involved (Smilde et al., 2014). Educators should consider bringing their student musicians to care facilities to engage in intergenerational musical collaborations. Those with dementia are often thought of as living in a “wasteland for learning,” however some scholars suggest those with dementia can in fact demonstrate musical learning (Quinn & Blandon, 2017;), musical creativity (Dusman; 2020) and have an appreciation for music even in latter stages of the disease (Riley, 2009). Moreover, intergenerational musical encounters and collaborations between youth and those with dementia can be successful with college students, k-12 students, and even infants. Examples of successful intergenerational musical activities include choir, songwriting, singing nursery rhymes, or ‘person-centered improvisations.’

Intergenerational Choirs

Forming intergenerational choirs with students and those with dementia can yield mutual benefits. Harris & Capporella (2014), inspired by ‘contact theory’ (Allport, 1954), started an intergenerational choir and utilized the ‘buddy system’ between the two groups in effort to combat stigmas associated with those with dementia. Contact theory asserts that contact between different groups in optimal conditions has the potential to reduce prejudice. Results from choir observations show a decrease in social isolation for those with dementia. Participating college students were found to have a decrease in negative attitudes and increase in positive attitudes; moreover, themes regarding reduced stigma and reduced social

discomfort emerged, suggesting an expansion of understanding among students regarding dementia. Similar findings were displayed by (Conway & Hodgman, 2008), where participants expressed a better understanding of others, and a disappearance of age barriers. However, challenges did emerge regarding preparation for performance collaboration and issues regarding space orientation of ensemble singers.

Intergenerational Nursery Rhythms Singing

Even infants have been taken into dementia care units to engage musically with the elderly. Children between the ages of 3 months and 5 years old were part of an intergenerational program involving the singing nursery rhythms with those suffering from neurodegeneration (McLennan, 2019). Sessions utilized well-known songs in effort to provide more familiar musical entry points for the older generations. Musical growth was reported with musical skills gained by both children, nursery practitioners and the elderly. Moreover, the development of confidence and social skills were found in all participants. In addition, emergent themes of 'happy,' 'energized,' and 'uplifted' were noted in questionnaires.

Intergenerational Songwriting

Songwriting can also be a viable option for engaging with those in dementia care facilities. In a study by Dusman (2020), elementary school students collaborated with those in a memory care unit, in eight sessions of original storytelling/ songwriting. The participatory and creative process was found to be valuable in 'making space' for participants and most importantly, honoring their diverse routes in the creative process. Further, children, in particular "demonstrated an increase in cross-generational connection" (Dusman, 2020, p.6).

Intergenerational Musical Improvisation

Finally, improvisation can be a powerful tool when musically connecting with those facing neurodegeneration. The 'Music for Life' (Wigmore Hall in London) project engages musicians with those suffering from dementia in a 'person-centered' improvisatory space in effort to make the person behind the disease visible again (Smilde et al., 2014). Music for Life's Daisy Swift, explains that "people can live well with dementia, provided their given creative space, that their voices are heard and they can connect

with others, and they're valued as equals" (TessituraNetwork, 2019). In these encounters, musicians ebb and flow with care facility residents as the elderly sing or improvise melodic fragments only to be built upon by the visiting musicians; it is a demonstration of musical democracy and liberation, and for musicians specifically, it can be an exercise in empathy where 'music is generated by the musicians for the residents' (Smilde et al., 2014, p. 247). The musician must 'tune-in' to what those suffering from dementia are feeling or trying to express. The process can be incredibly formative for participants, leading to inner inquiry, and an investigation of the self as a musician, and as a person existing in a confounding world. A violinist named Frank offered his reflective words:

"Doing this work has been a way for me to connect my musicianship with a deepening sense of who I am in this world, brought about by extraordinary interactions with extraordinary people ... This work continues to teach me who I am, and is a benchmark against which I judge everything else I do. It's extraordinary how working with people whose version of reality is so vague can in fact be the ultimate reality check!" (Smilde, Page and Alheit 2014: 13).

Participating musicians are not the only ones who benefit from these interactions. Those with dementia are operating within a framework of exploration where each moment, however fleeting, is an opportunity for engagement and learning through musical discovery; it is in these seemingly brief moments that the beauties of life manifest.

Conclusion

Centering music education within a cosmopolitan framework expands the meaning and purpose of the profession, thereby justifying an expansion of horizons regarding the spaces, places, and people included in the purview of the field. In doing so, it allows an understanding of those battling dementia as worthy of musical engagement. Moreover, extant literature describes possible ways for music educators (and their students) to provide life giving musical experiences to those with dementia while in turn, creating transformative learning experiences for all participants involved. However, research on intergenerational music engagement regarding those with dementia is limited and the imagination of music educators is necessary to find new ways to engage musically, and new populations to connect with.

Cosmopolitanism as a framework for music education and its “ethical sensitivity towards human connection” (Niknafs, 2020, p.3) extends beyond just those with dementia and should be considered as a guiding force for the future endeavors of music educators. If music is a distinctly human phenomenon, if we become more human through music making, and if cosmopolitanism music education is about human connection, then I suggest the role of the music educator is to deepen and diversify human connections and transmit musical knowledge that leads to a greater understanding of what it means to be human. This understanding of music education can take us far beyond the K-12 classroom and into homeless shelters, rehab centers, hospitals, and elderly care facilities to work with adolescents or adults struggling with addiction, children battling deadly illnesses, or any marginalized community living in the absence of music. Moreover, this philosophy reaches beyond certified K-12 educators, and includes church choirs, community orchestras, singer songwriters, rock musicians, DJ’s and any musician with the capacity and desire to connect musically to improve the lives of their fellow human beings.

In conclusion, music educators pervade cities, towns and villages around the nation. Their presence is felt from small rural farming communities to urban metropolises. With 1 in 5 Americans expected to reach 65 or older by the year 2030 (RHH, 2021), communities around the country will be facing growing numbers of dementia cases within their localities. Music educators have the knowledge, power and resources to improve the lives of these people. Teachers can begin by reaching out to their respective local communities and make connections with dementia care facilities, offering to bring in performers or facilitate intergenerational musical collaborations. In centering music education in human connection, and the desire to alleviate human suffering, music educators have the moral responsibility to both their students, and those in their community struggling with dementia, to reach out to these marginalized groups and bring music where it is needed.

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